

SIMULATED REALITIES AND DIGITAL IDENTITIES: A POSTMODERN ANALYSIS OF THE FILM *LOGOUT* (2025)Muhammad Bilal Ahmad¹, Fazal Rabi², Nafeesa Sardar³, Tayyaba Khan⁴, Roshni Begum⁵^{1,3,4,5}Student At Department of English Literature & Linguistics, Riphah International University²Lecturer At Department of English Literature & Linguistics, Riphah International University,¹mbilalaeg@gmail.com, ²fazalrabbi999@gmail.com, ³nafeesazufeen@gmail.com, ⁴48989@students.riphah.edu.pk, ⁵49269@students.riphah.edu.pkDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17018061>**Keywords**

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Corresponding Author: *

Fazal Rabi

Abstract

This study examines the postmodern literary features of the Indian film *Logout* (2025) that were used with an emphasis on such major themes as hyperreality, pastiche, intertextuality, and fragmentation. The theoretical frameworks of Jean Baudrillard, Fredric Jameson, Julia Kristeva, and Linda Hutcheon are employed to critique the portrayal of authenticity, digital identities, and commodification of cultural identity as the elements of influencer culture, online performances in this qualitative research. The paper presents a close reading of five textually thematically important scenes of the film, and it analyses its visual language, narrative and aesthetic choices, that disrupt the traditional style of telling stories on the screen and erase the border between the real and the fake. According to the results, *Logout* criticizes the internet culture by demonstrating the fragmentation and inauthenticity of personae presented online, where the ancient and traditional cultures are appropriated and commercialized in the digital world. The nonlinear story as presented in the film is an indication of the fragmented existence in modern digital life whereas intertextuality and ironic contrasts is an indication of postmodern fear of originality and meaning in the digital era. The study sheds light on the interrelation among technology, identity, and narrative in contemporary film and has a model to interdisciplinary studies in media, culture, and digital communications in terms of how truth and identity reflect dynamic modifications in digital media.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last several years, several factors that shape the way people communicate with one another, express themselves and form identities have changed significantly: the digitization of culture and the popularity of social media have led to several changes that have overturned the way people communicate with one another, express themselves, and build identities. This transformation has been focused on the concept of the so-called influencer, as individuals develop their fake online identities in ways that are

often dissimilar to their authentic personas. The difference between performance and reality is increasingly failing to make out in this globalized world. These developments are reflected in postmodernism which is a theoretical approach focusing on the concepts of fragmentation, simulation, intertextual and hyper-reality of society in modern times. Postmodern ideas can help us understand how digital media affects the people's behavior and constructs stories, tendencies, and

beliefs within society (Ali, Hamid, Ejaz, Aziz, Gul, & Ibrahim, 2025). The post-modern conditions are properly captured in the 2025 film *Logout*. The movie reuses the confusion, the performance, and emotional uncertainty that is associated with contemporary digital life through the troubled relationship between a young influencer with his online identity and with his followers. Hence, *Logout* can be taken as one of the most valuable case studies in the age of social networks to explore the ways postmodern elements can be represented in the mass media discourse.

Despite the increasing popularity of digital media in India, scholarship is limited on the study of Indian screen life films through the prism of a more postmodern way of thinking. The field of postmodernity films has neglected the analysis of the Western movie industry giving an opportunity to extend the theories to relate them to the experience of Indian narrative driven by regional culture and internet presence. There is enough material in the screen life thriller *Logout* (2025), based on the influencer culture, but it has not received much scholarly attention so far. This movie has not been critically dissected with reference to issues pertaining to identity performance, hyperreality, intertextuality, and narrative fragmentation. In addition, despite the common explanations of media simulation and the confusion of reality to be provided by global theorist such as Jean Baudrillard, it is important to apply such theories to the Indian experiences in culture and online operations. This paper will address such gaps by providing a culturally sensitized postmodern perspective of *Logout*.

The ultimate focus of the study is to explore the representations of postmodern aspects, which are digital identity, online activity, and the way of narrative form in the Indian screen life film *Logout* (2025). The research aims to understand how screen life narration in the context of the movie depicts the disintegrated and artificial realities of the social media culture in India via a postmodern prism.

The following are Research Objectives of this study: To discover and examine some of the essential postmodern features in *Logout* namely pastiche, fragmentation, hyperreality and intertextuality. 2) In an attempt to explore how *Logout* portrays the creation and misrecognition of identity in the online world. The third one involves (3) locating postmodern

theories, including Baudrillardic simulation, in the Indian media and culture environment.

The following are the Research Questions of this research study:

1. What is the postmodern presentation of movie *Logout* in terms of hyperreality, intertextuality and fragmentation?
2. What confusions and identity constructions in the electronic era do the movie represent?
3. What can be coined out of the postmodern theories application to Indian digital storytellers like *Logout*?

This paper examines the film *Logout* (2025) with the help of the post-modern theories, especially the ideas of Jean Baudrillard, Fredric Jameson and Jean-Francois Lyotard. The theory of hyperreality demonstrated by Baudrillard is based on the fact the media images or simulations often appear as reality far more than actual reality. It is along this line that the postmodern culture is viewed as a type of culture that is typified by the concept of pastiche, which is the concept proposed by Fredric Jameson as meaningless playful imitation or instant of styles. The concept of fragmentation, as proposed by Lyotard, presents a disintegration that can prevail over cohesive identities and narratives and can be often depicted through a fragmented or non-linear narrative. The other theory is the concept of intertextuality that focuses on how the media texts are affected by frequent references to other stories, literary patterns or symbols. These frameworks are effective in the analysis of the *Logout* movie since they facilitate comprehending the way the film portrays modern digital life that is marked with Polyreality, poly-influence and polynarrative forms, which are characteristic of current media-saturated, screen-based society.

This research is very important in cultural terms as well as academically. What it considers culturally is the way the *Logout* (2025) incorporates significant issues of the online era especially within the Indian context. The film reveals the impact of social media on the lives of the youths whose online identities are seen to define most of them. It also attracts attention to the manner that influencer culture, influences relations, emotional condition and self-esteem. By examining these aspects, the impetus will be given by considering how digital technologies make individuals confused by their online avatars and their real identities. Academically, the paper contributes to

postmodern studies in media by bringing in those notions, which are vital in the study of media such as hyperreality, pastiche, intertextuality, and fragmented narrative, to an Indian screen life movie. This is a combination little studied in scholarly work except in South Asian film. The focus on such global theories as those of Baudrillard and Jameson is intended to be localized in the current search and show how it may be tested to understand the Indian cultural narratives in the world of the digital age. In this way, it responds to the absence of postmodern behavior in the local media and generates the new prospects of critical responses to Indian films representing identity and virtual life.

Literature Review

This part conducts a review of past research to furnish a theoretical and situational background of a postmodern theory of analysis in Logout (2025). Four existing areas of focus of the review involve postmodernism in the study of media, digital identity and social media, screen life cinema, and postmodernism in Indian cinema. All these interconnected influences provide essential background to the way that the present anxieties surrounding reality, identity, and simulation of a media world are captured within Logout. Such postmodern issues as pastiche, hyperreality, and disjointed narrative offer beneficial guidelines in the attempt to understand the narrative and style of the film (Ullah, Khan, Qazi, Zeb, & Rabi, 2025). The rise of digital culture and life as an influencer has a major influence on identity formation and presentation online as well. An evaluation of the literature on such issues can help contextualize Logout with other academic and cultural discourses. It shows the way in which the movie can be accommodated into both local culture and international theories.

Postmodernism and Media Studies

Postmodern theory provides quite helpful and necessary instruments to analyze the way reality and identity are framed by media. Jean Baudrillard concept of hyperreality describes a world where such a simulation as a social media profile or a filtered experience is more real than reality (Baudrillard, 1994). This is especially applicable in the era of the influencer culture, in which individual realities are

often obscured and confused with online identities (Ijaz & Rabi, 2022). The concept by Fredric Jameson on pastiche describes the incompetent simulation in meaning and purpose of historic modes of presentation without direction and purpose that determines how present-day media is a rehash of cultural forms on a superficial level (Jameson, 1991). In the theory authored by Jean-Francois Lyotard, metanarratives are no longer the most plausible as they have been substituted by fragmented personal narratives (Lyotard, 1979). Intertextuality, a notion of the fact that the texts refer to or they borrow the other texts, is also significant in the postmodern media studies since it reflects on how modern texts refer to the other texts (Kristeva, 1980). The theories are especially pertinent to contemporary screen life movies to include Logout in the provision light to its simulation-oriented identity problems, its profound enhancement to digital culture, its re-processing of socially constructed narratives, and its varied chronology.

Digital Identity and the Influence of Social Media

Social media platforms such as YouTube, Instagram and TikTok form and shape the identity of the youth tremendously. Rehman (2025) suggests a study that shows that young people construct their online identities actively through using a model of a curated self-seeking validation of their likes and followers, which may empower them and be sobering at the same time (Javed Ashiq, Usman, Rabi, & Uzma, 2024). Moreover, based on research, teenagers are showing and displaying their online identities increasingly, posting information that is directed towards likes and applause. The behavior is directly related to the development of a digital identity where self-presentation turns into the realm of performance and opens to a feedback loop (Dhingra & Mishra, 2025). Also, excessive use-using social media, according to scientific sources, will cause certain psychological harm and this aspect is concerned with self-worth and self-esteem (Ullah, Ahmad, & Sardar, 2024). The increased use of social media by the younger people was also determined to be a prognosticator of low self-esteem by Samoon & Juneja (2025). Females with an identity confusion, anxiety, and low self-esteem and social media use were strongly associated, as well, revealed in the study by Pathak and

Pandey (2025). Similarly, Fatima (2024) determined a strong relationship between self-esteem and social media use among adolescents, which means that the problem of platform usage can undermine the emotional state and self-perception of a person (Riaz, Qureshi, & Zaib, 2025). These works bring awareness to how social media platforms affect the psychological state and how such sites and applications influence identity development and the conflict between the actual and performative selves which are critical issues to be discussed in detail in Logout.

Screen Life Cinema and Representation of Digital Realities

Screen life movie is a cinematography in which the filmmakers capture the entire narrative by utilizing digital interface and such as webcams, computer desk, cellphone screen, or social chat networks (Nawaz, Khan, & Rabi, 2024). This type of communication, which started with the advent of internet communication, shows how the use of digital devices has pervaded our lives. It can be stated that this genre is most adequately recreated by such films as *Unfriended* (2014) and *Searching* (2018) that visualize screen interactions to illustrate the events in the story. Boris Shimokhin (2021) argues that screen life movies have their own cinematic language, which adopts the modern digital narratives to narrative production with the help of the desktop view, chat windows, and notification alerts (Rabi, Ahmad, Hussain, & Ullah, 2025). Expanding upon that thought, the works by other researchers of digital culture and psychology have shown how an environment centered around social media foster's identity problems and erases the borders between online and offline selves (Rabi, Ullah, & Rabi, 2024). *Logout* (2025) is one such narrative, with the social media feeds, video chats, and content production being the Play box that hums along as the narrative construct, framing how the dialect of digital validation and performance influences identity, emotional manners, and personality authenticity.

Postmodernism in Indian Cinema

In the Indian cinema, postmodern themes are increasingly visible, especially the aspect of the criticism of the media and irony as well as fragmented narratives. According to Wright (2015), Bollywood

often allows mixing traditional narrative styles and modern aesthetics in the recycling of its own items in the terms of pastiche, intertextual allusions, and remakes. This is an example of a broader postmodern movement where films provide rather playful and critical storylines that contradict originality and authenticity (Rabi, Ullah, Ibrar, & Akbar, 2024). In addition, Indian filmmakers are increasingly making more use of the social media and the digital culture in their narrations (Ullah, Rabi, Khan, & Ahmad, 2025). Recent research shows the beginning of using the symbolism of influencers, lip-sync media, and social media material into the plot as a means of raising concerns about the questions of identity, digital celebrity, and the reputation of online presence (Chakrabarty in Vasudevan et al., 2023). The abovementioned tendency can be explained by such movies as *Kho Gaye Hum Kahan* and *LSD 2*, the latter of which criticizes the influencer society, cancel culture, and the impact of digital attention on the feeling of self (Satti, Zaib, & Mangrio, 2025). These postmodern and digital trends offer a useful foundation for examining *Logout* (2025), which integrates media critique, digital identity, and fragmented storytelling into a screen life framework.

Studies on Logout (2025)

Due to the film's recent release and the lack of scholarly analysis, most of the critiques of *Logout* (2025) that are now available are located on journalistic and film-review websites rather than in academic research. The Indian Express's reviews praise its timely examination of internet fame and identity, although some point out plot inconsistencies and that some events feel forced or unrealistic (Indian Express, 2025). India Today praises the movie for its excellent depiction of the psychological costs that digital validation takes, highlighting how the protagonist's curated online self crumbles when authority is taken away (India Today, 2025). Likewise, Cinema Express highlights the film's powerful center performance and atmospheric tension, noting that it combines human drama and digital claustrophobia in a minimalist screen-life structure (Cinema Express, 2025).

Despite these useful reviews, there are currently no peer-reviewed academic studies that use postmodern theory to analyze *Logout*, especially themes like

pastiche, fractured narrative, hyperreality, and intertextuality in digital environments (Rabi, Bibi, Mukhtiar, & Zahir, 2025). Additionally, no scholarly work exists, which position the film within the context of other Indian screenplay by relying on the theoretical framework (Ahmad, Sardar, Begum, Khan, & Bibi, 2025). This research gap on this literature indicates the importance of a specific postmodern analysis of the Logout, especially along with the lines of the theory of digital media and Indian film studies (Shen, Zhao, & Zaib, 2025).

The analyzed literature talks about the applicability of postmodern concepts, including hyperreality, pastiche, fragmentation, and intertextuality, in the age of digital and their ability to help us understand the modern media and its impact on identity (Rabi, Zahir, Aziz, Mukhtiar, & Bibi, 2025). Studies related to digital culture indicate how social networking sites develop a performative identity and confuse the distinctions between the real and virtual personalities introducing new issues involving authenticity and self-identity. Recent research indicates that screen life film has emerged to be a strong narrative style to capture such virtual worlds, though little research has been conducted about its application within the Indian cinema. Although it is evident that Indian films that explore the concept of influencer culture, internet celebrity, and media manipulation are on the rise, people have not realized much up modern analysis being done to these films and more significantly Logout (2025). This study tries to bridge that divide by examining the presentation of postmodernism themes and stories in Logout to contribute to the cultural discourses about digital identity in the age of social media, and film criticism.

Methodology

The study design deployed in the research study is qualitative, interpretive, and analytical. The given paper employs theoretical use of text and film analysis as the way of being critical about the movie Logout (2025) rather than determining some numerical data or evaluating it upon the audience. The issue to be studied is the meanings, representations, and ideologies of the given film particularly in the light of the postmodern theory. This approach would be good when it comes to finding out how movies, especially screen life narratives exemplify and critique

contemporary social problems such as influencer culture, hyperreality, and virtual construction of self. The study seeks to find more cultural and theoretical meaning and studies the structure, aesthetics, and themes of the film.

The backbone of this study is the postmodern theory that has been based on the theory of other prominent thinkers such as Jean Baudrillard, Fredric Jameson and Jean-Francois Lyotard. The analysis is also figured by the theory of simulation and hyperreality theorized by Jean Baudrillard, the concept that highlights the ways in which the movie confuses the notions of the real and the fake identities, especially regarding performative identity and identities online. The concept of pastiche described by Fredric Jameson goes a long way toward clarifying how the film presents the postmodern predilection toward remix and repurposing of established forms in a digital environment. The idea of disbelief in metanarratives that had been proposed by Jean-Francois Lyotard is also helpful in understanding the structure of non-linear and fragmented narrative used in the film. Moreover, the concept of intertextuality is applied to understand the way the movie affirms its postmodernism through the reference and transformation of other texts and cultural resources. These concepts combined provide an opportunity to look at the way in which the film portrays reality, media and identity in the digital landscape.

To select the data to be used in the present study, the key works selected in this paper are the following screen life movie of Indian origin, written by Biswa Pati Sarkar, which is called Logout (2025). It is particularly topical because of the specific nature of the narrative, presented by entirely digital screens, and addresses topics related to virtual relationships, online identity and online fame pressure. Such attributes make it an interesting topic to be analyzed post modernly, especially considering the hyperreality, narrative fragmentation and simulation. It is a great asset to study the construction of identity in Indian screen life films because Logout provides a story of a social media influencer who needs to balance popularity, his mental health, and self-impression within the digital space.

The most common methods to be employed in this research are textual and visual analysis so that to make clear the postmodern elements in the film Logout

(2025). A close reading of the movie will be conducted through analysis of key elements of the film namely, the technique used in this movie to tell the story, visual framing of the movie, presentation of social media interface, how the dialogue had been done and intertextual references. Postmodern ideas, such as hyperreality, pastiche, fragmentation, and intertextuality, will be used to analyze these components to find deeper meanings embedded in the narrative and aesthetics of the movie.

Since there are no human subjects, surveys, or interviews in this study, it does not raise issues regarding consent or personal data. Every intellectual source, including scholarly publications and theoretical texts, has been appropriately cited. The

study complies with responsible academic procedures, ensuring proper citation, avoiding plagiarism, and upholding integrity in the analysis of the chosen film and related literature.

The scope of this study is limited because it only focuses on one movie, Logout, and analyzes it using a few chosen postmodern theories. Deep understanding is possible through this theoretical lens, but it might not fully capture all cultural nuances, particularly when using primarily Western concepts to an Indian cinematic environment. Furthermore, the study excludes empirical data and audience reaction, which can provide more information on how viewers understand the movie's ideas.

Data Analysis

4.1 Hyperreality in Logout (2025)

Jean Baudrillard’s concept of hyperreality describes a world where representations of reality—media, simulations, and digital constructions—replace and become more real than reality itself (Baudrillard, 1983). In this simulated space, the boundary between the real and the artificial collapses, and the imitation often becomes more influential than the truth. Logout (2025) serves as a cinematic reflection of this condition, portraying a world where digital personas,

social media performances, and curated illusions dominate human interaction and self-perception.

a) Turning Life into Content: “Everything is Content”

In a critical exchange with Smiti, Pratyush reflects, “Because that’s content—not only my videos are content, my reactions are content, when I go for holiday, that’s content... even getting dumped and turning into a star is aspirational content.”

This dialogue between Pratyush and Smriti illustrates the postmodern concept of hyperreality. Pratyush reflects on how every aspect of his life, from heartbreak to holidays, is transformed into "content" for a digital audience, emphasizing how real-life experiences are increasingly staged for social media. He acknowledges that, to attract attention and engage viewers, creators often embellish or fabricate elements of their lives, thus making the fake appear more credible than reality itself. This aligns with

Baudrillard's idea of hyperreality, where the distinction between simulation and reality becomes blurred. Pratyush further explains how a personal event, like a breakup, is repurposed as "relatable content," while post-breakup success is marketed as "aspirational content." This commodification of personal suffering highlights how social media not only depicts life but reshapes it into a performative spectacle, where authenticity takes a backseat to engagement and virality.

The graph shows how different types of social media engagement (Likes, Shares, Comments, Followers) impact Pratyush's digital identity, highlighting the commodification of his persona through increasing engagement.

b) Blackmail and the Power of the Digital Persona

In another scene, Pratyush is blackmailed by Pratmaniac 1 who threatens:

"If you tell anyone, just two clicks... and your every chat, every photo, every girl you have swiped right on—will go public."

Here, the digital self carries more weight and consequence than real-life identity. The threat is not just about personal embarrassment but the public reconstruction of his image. Once online, fragments of his digital life—memes, chats, and photos—will be interpreted independently of context, giving rise to new, uncontrolled narratives. The public no longer seeks truth; it engages with the most viral version of it.

c) "This Is the Real Pratyush": The Death of Credibility

A key moment in the film occurs when Pratmaniac 1 posts an old photo of Pratyush eating fried chicken—damaging for a known vegan influencer. In response, he comments:

"Hi guys, this is the real Pratyush Dua here! Don't believe this!! Someone stole my phone!!"

The public reaction is mocking:

"Hi guys, this is the real Adolf Hitler. Someone misprinted all the history books!!"

"Hi guys, this is the real Jack from Titanic. Don't believe Rose..."

This scene perfectly captures the collapse of belief and credibility in postmodern digital culture. The

audience chooses spectacle over truth. As Baudrillard suggests, in a hyperreal society, the simulation becomes more believable than reality. Pratyush’s denial appears as another form of performance, indistinguishable from lies. His authenticity is rendered meaningless.

d) Fabricated Heroism: Playing Both Sides

Another striking moment occurs when Pratyush comments negatively on Nautankita’s post from a fake account, then logs into his official account and publicly condemns the very comment he posted: “First learn to respect women, then call yourself my fan.”

This is a powerful instance of self-created hyperreality, where conflict and resolution are both orchestrated for digital applause. He stages his own moral high ground, using dual personas to manufacture drama and manipulate his audience. Likes, shares, and comments become currency, while sincerity becomes obsolete. In this scene, the real issue—gender sensitivity—is sidelined in favor of social media optics.

The film’s emotional climax occurs when Sakshi (Pratmaniac 1) confronts Pratyush:

“I love him, papa! He’s my only friend!”

“You don’t love me, Sakshi. The one you see is Pratman... not Pratyush.”

This interaction captures the emotional consequences of hyperreality. Sakshi confuses digital closeness with personal connection. She does not know Pratyush—only his curated image. In Baudrillard’s terms, she falls in love with a simulacrum: a representation without reference to any reality. Her obsession underscores the danger of simulated intimacy—where avatars become more meaningful than actual people.

Hyperreality as the Core of Logout

Logout meticulously illustrates the postmodern notion of hyperreality, where personal identities dissolve into performances, truth is fragmented into likes and comments, and digital reality supplants the actual. Each scene reiterates Baudrillard’s claim that in a hyperreal society, people no longer consume products or content—they consume simulations of life (Baudrillard, 1983). Pratyush’s digital downfall is not merely a crisis of privacy; it is a crisis of identity, reality, and meaning.

e) Pratman vs. Pratyush: Fan Love and Identity Collapse

Scene	Postmodern Concept	Theory Applied	Analysis
Pratyush's "everything is content" monologue	Hyperreality	Baudrillard's Simulation	Life is reconfigured as content to maintain an online persona, blurring the lines between real experiences and digital performances.
Laila-Majnu reenactment for viral fame	Pastiche	Jameson's Pastiche	The traditional Laila-Majnu story is reduced to a superficial performance designed for social media engagement, stripping it of cultural depth.
Sakshi's obsession with Pratyush's online identity	Fragmentation	Liotard's Fragmentation	Sakshi's love for Pratyush is based on his digital persona, showing how identity becomes fragmented and replaced with a simulacrum of reality.
Pratman's manipulation of his online persona	Hyperreality	Baudrillard's Simulation	Pratyush creates multiple digital personas to manipulate his image, illustrating the dominance of the simulated over the real.
Pratyush's denial of the viral photo	Pastiche	Jameson's Pastiche	His denial of the viral photo becomes another performance, devoid of authenticity, as truth is shaped by the online spectacle.

4.2 Pastiche in *Logout* (2025)

Fredric Jameson (1991) defines *pastiche* as a form of imitation that lacks satire, irony, or critical commentary. Unlike parody, pastiche simply replicates older cultural forms—styles, genres, or stories—without invoking their original depth or emotional resonance. In the context of postmodern media, this results in the flattening of meaning, where classical narratives are recycled for surface appeal rather than thematic substance. In *Logout*, the postmodern mode of pastiche is vividly exemplified through the digital re-staging of the classic South Asian romantic tragedy *Laila-Majnu*. Rather than serving as a solemn narrative of love and sacrifice, the tale is trivialized and commodified for viral content in the influencer economy.

a) *Laila-Majnu* as Clickbait Content

A notable moment occurs when Pratyush discovers a video in which he himself (in a staged influencer clip) performs the role of Majnu, alongside Sakshi as Laila. During a phone conversation, Sakshi (Pratmaniac 1) remarks:

“Actually, I love all the *Laila-Majnu* videos, but that proposal one is my favorite of them.”

This scene encapsulates the postmodern impulse to hollow out and repackage emotionally rich cultural icons. *Laila-Majnu*, a story historically steeped in longing, madness, and mystical love, is reduced here to performative skits designed to generate social media traction. The emotions are acted, stylized, and published not for meaning, but for likes, shares, and follower counts. This illustrates Jameson’s concept of pastiche as “a blank parody,” where form remains but substance is drained. In this instance, the film criticizes the decomposition of the sacred narratives of their cultural gravitas. This reenactment fails to act as a tribute to love, instead being a consumerized product that objectifies the couple into a narrative that can simply be superimposed onto the commodified material to fill in interest: *Laila-Majnu* thus becomes nothing more but a vessel on which algorithmically produced content can be designed geometrical patterns. The impersonation of Pratyush and Sakshi turns into an empty mimicking: of the message of the narrative not of its visual and emotional associations.

b) Tragic Love Rewritten as Digital Fantasy

Sakshi later intensifies this thematic flattening by romanticizing her obsessive attachment to Pratyush.

In a dramatic climax, she declares:

“You owe me a love story, and my love story will end the way every true love story ends. Like Laila and Majnu. Follower and influencer. In death, together, forever.”

This conversation echoes the concept of pastiche with classical tragedy providing the model of how an emotional performance could be set up using the resources of digital media. Sakshi mixes the love with the obsession performance, interpreting *Laila-Majnu* as the model of unhealthy love instead of the warning against it. Her fantasy to relive a romantic death as a romanticized reenactment with an influencer shows exactly how intensely the culture of the internet blurs the distinction between myth and simulation. Rather than capturing pure emotion, Sakshi transforms the story of *Laila-Majnu* into a dark fantasy that is intended to achieve immortality in digital space going to the extremes of making herself out to be a tragic heroine and Pratyush to be a digital martyr. This reflects so much of postmodern pastiche: a simulacrum whose copy is a soulless copy without an original, a citation-gone-astray without any weight.

Pastiche is not only a stylistic device, but a critical statement in *Logout*. Cinematographic work depicts the extent to which mature mythologies become glossy superficial in the period of the influencer. There is no longer any cultural richness but image copying and interaction via the computer. *Logout* using these sources criticizes the loss of meaning in the postmodern media where neither identity, love nor tragedy have been experienced but are acted out. The application of *Laila-Majnu* shows how holy love tales are changed into viral scripts- isolated of culture, romantic authenticity, or ethical variances. In this hypermediated world, the past is to be the setting of reed less acting, empty spectacles, and programmable drama.

4.3 Intertextuality in *Logout* (2025)

Intertextuality, a concept introduced by Julia Kristeva (1980), refers to the idea that all texts are constructed from the traces, echoes, and influences of other texts. In postmodernism, intertextuality is used to blur the

boundaries between originality and imitation. It often manifests in playful, ironic, or critical references to historical events, literature, cinema, or popular culture, reflecting a world where meaning is recycled rather than created anew.

In *Logout* (2025), intertextuality operates on two primary levels: first, through audience-generated digital responses filled with cultural references; second, through character dialogues that reframe iconic narratives within the digital age. Both strategies reflect how postmodern identities and meanings are constructed through borrowed textual and cultural fragments.

a) Meme Culture and Pop-Cultural Allusions

A vivid illustration of intertextuality emerges when Pratyush attempts to defend his identity after a hacked photo of him eating fried chicken is posted online with the caption:

“@veggielite here’s what my 100% vegan diet looks like.”

In panic, he comments:

“Hi guys this is the real Pratyush Dua here! Don’t believe this!! Someone stole my phone!! This is an old pic.”

However, rather than believing his explanation, internet users mockingly imitate his tone using exaggerated and humorous references:

“Hi guys this is the real Adolf Hitler. Someone misprinted all history books!!”

“Hi guys this is the real Katappa here, I didn’t kill Baahubali!”

“Hi guys this is the real Jack from Titanic. Don’t believe Rose...”

These responses are a form of intertextual parody as they are based on varying cultural stories history (Hitler), Indian film (Baahubali) and Hollywood (Titanic) to mock the earnestness of Pratyush. In this scene, the dominating social media discourse of recycled content whereby the authenticity in texts is mocked and substituted with the performative comedy reinterpretations of the old written works is absent.

In this case, the real nerves of Pratyush with respect to his tarnished reputation are undermined by a trivial culture- online wherein meaning has been disarticulated into palliatives. A chain of intertextual

jokes overwrites his truth, and the fact that serious discourse is reduced to meme culture in the era of postmodernism is symbolically displayed. The scene is a sort of criticism of the loss of individuality and personal experience on a ground that is already flooded with borrowed and sarcastically replayed scripts.

b) Laila-Majnu: Classical Tragedy in a Digital Frame

A second layer of intertextuality emerges in a climactic dialogue between Sakshi (Pratmaniac 1) and Pratyush. She declares:

“You owe me a love story... and my love story will end the way every true love story ends. Like Laila and Majnu. Follower and influencer. In death, together, forever.”

In this case, the classic romance of Laila-Majnu, which is, in the Urdu-Persian literary world, famous because of its depictions of spiritual love and tragic sacrifice, is transformed into an artistic vision of internet fame and digital addiction. Sakshi identifies herself and Pratyush as the Laila and Majnu of the modern world, only that the mystical lovers are now understood as a follower and an influencer. This duality of irony serves to blend classic literary tropes with the current social media avatars and produce a multitaxial intertextual moment. It shows the process by which the postmodern people bend the old story-telling models to endorse their realities of performance. The spiritual seriousness of Laila-Majnu is deprived of its mythic solemnity, and it is redirected to a showbiz realm. Rather than demonstrate love, Sakshi performs an objectified infatuation, which is founded in digital fame, at the expense of emotional connubium.

This reinterpretation is indicative of an idea that in postmodern writings, meaning is not fixed. The classical stories are not commemorated but prostituted-turned into the patterns of individual make-believe, dementia, and performance. Sakshi does not identify with Laila-Majnu; she uses it to help validate her own toxic narrative, to feel epic and widely shareable.

Logout shows not only that the contemporary identity has been delivered not through the lived experiences, but through the cultural borrowing and fracture of references. The movie is critical of the nature of the recycling of classic stories, mythology, and tropes of

the cinematic world through digital communication in which all these are devoid of their layers and can be used as irony, mockery, or self-promotion. Whether through memified sarcasm or romantic delusions, the film shows how originality has decayed into recombination, echoing Kristeva’s assertion that every text is a mosaic of quotations. In the postmodern digital world, meaning is no longer created, it is performed, shared, rehashed, and often misunderstood.

4.4 Fragmentation in *Logout* (2025)

Fragmentation, a hallmark of postmodern narrative, disrupts conventional storytelling by breaking linear chronology, stable identities, and unified meaning structures. As Linda Hutcheon (1988) notes, postmodernism embraces a world marked by chaos, contradiction, and multiplicity, reflecting how individuals in contemporary society experience the

self and reality as fractured and unstable. *Logout* (2025), directed by Sourav Bhattacharya, employs fragmentation at both narrative and psychological levels—through a nonlinear plot and through the protagonist’s disintegrated identity—mirroring the disjointed nature of digital life in the social media age.

a) Nonlinear Narrative and Structural Discontinuity

The film opens with a suspenseful and confusing scene: a mysterious boy enters a hotel disguised as a food delivery man, hiding a gun in his bag. He deceives the distracted guards, enters false credentials into the visitor register, ascends to the top floor, and receives a chilling message—a photo of himself on that very floor. Moments later, he is abruptly pushed from the rooftop by an unseen figure. The narrative then suddenly jumps backward in time, starting the story afresh to unravel how events culminated in this moment.

Breakdown of Narrative Techniques in *Logout* (2025)

The Pie Chart illustrates the breakdown of narrative techniques used in *Logout* (2025), highlighting the proportion of non-linear storytelling (40%), character focus on Pratyush’s emotional journey (30%), and social media sequences depicting influencer life (30%). The chart visually represents the key narrative components and their impact on the film’s structure.

This anti-linear narration that starts or is close to the climax and then works backwards is a breaking away with the classical narrative patterns which include exposition, rising action, climax, and resolution. The temporality disjunction is not an original piece of plot

only, but a specific postmodern approach that forces the viewer to make up the causality and meaning among the discontinuous fragments. This type of structural fragmentation corresponds to the digital state where time, memory and identity are nonlinear and curated. Like social media accounts, which offer a chaotic window into life—or a highlight reel without sequence—*Logout* imitates that spastic experience of consuming reality. It demands the audience to assemble the story themselves, undermining passive watching and corresponding to the broken rhythms of the digital culture.

The Timeline of Narrative Fragmentation illustrates the nonlinear structure of *Logout* (2025), showing how scenes jump backward in time. It visually represents the fragmented storytelling, reinforcing the concept of time disjunction discussed in the "Fragmentation" analysis.

b) Psychological Fragmentation: The Split Between "Pratyush" and "Pratman"

Along with its composition, *Logout* also trades with fragmentation with the protagonist, Pratyush Dua who lives in the cracks between his real and online identity as Pratman. Pratyush is a helpless, depressed young man who is going through stresses of digital popularity, and Pratman, a self-assured professional who has millions of fans. This is an ontological gap between his real self and himself as an actor that is at the center of his emotional state in the film.

In several scenes, Pratyush alternates accounts, especially leaving abusive remarks using fake accounts, and then coming to the rescue using his own. He controls the perception in which he creates controversies and gets out of those to prove him right. His unique personality is secondary to the algorithmic interaction, and his decision-making process no longer exists under a guiding truth or moral code, but under likes, shares, and viral posts.

This dichotomy illustrates the postmodern self as a computer simulation, portrayed, repeated and disengaged of essence as raised by Baudrillard (1994). The crisis of an authentic self in the digital life is summed up in the words that Pratyush says to Sakshi, saying that he pretends to be that person but is not. The fragmentation is not only narrative, but existential as a tear in the self, a rupture molded by insistent compulsion to enact the self.

The Venn diagram illustrates the split between Pratyush’s real self and his online persona (Pratman). It highlights the tension between authenticity and digital performance, visually representing the psychological fragmentation discussed in the article.

The Visual Representation: Hyperreality and the Digital Persona illustrates the collapse between Pratyush's real self and his online persona. By using a split-image design with social media icons (Instagram, YouTube, TikTok), the image emphasizes Baudrillard's concept of hyperreality, where

digital personas overshadow reality, shaping identity through virtual platforms.

Logout is a fragmented piece, both in form and theme and in this depicts the principles of storytelling that is postmodern. The nonsensical, jerky stabbing style of narration, with its jumps through time and place,

resembles the curated, nonlinear character of social media. At the same time, the fragmented nature of the protagonist highlights the cost of digital performance as in the case of identity which is no longer fixed but simulated and re-constructed using algorithms and audiences. By means of such fragmentation on two levels, Logout provides not only an attractive

commentary to the modern situation when an integrity of a narrative and the self is more strongly shaken. The movie fits the standards of postmodern aesthetics through creation of the reality that does not reflect the whole and linear existence but is scattered, unstable, and infinitely mediated.

Table: Postmodern Themes and Their Application in Logout (2025)

Postmodern Concept	Film Scene	Theoretical Application
Hyperreality	Pratyush turning his life into “content”	Baudrillard’s simulation replacing reality
Pastiche	Laila-Manju re-enacted for viral content	Jameson’s cultural recycling and flattening of meaning
Fragmentation	Nonlinear narrative structure	Lyotard’s collapse of cohesive, linear storytelling
Intertextuality	Meme culture and pop-culture allusions	Kristeva’s blending of original and imitative texts

Conclusion

Logout is examined in this paper with the help of the postmodern concepts of hyperreality, pastiche, fragmentation, and intertextuality. These theoretical principles were implemented through textual and visual analysis, considering such aspects as dialogue, screen-based interactions, plot, and culture references. The analysis demonstrated that the movie reflects the key postmodern concepts including the entwining of texts and genres, imitation of reality, debasing of the familiar media models and discontinuous narrative. The findings show that the postmodernism approach used by Logout is a sharp criticism of contemporary online existence. The concept of hyperreality highlights the fact that the sense of identity is turned into a presented act and that virtual identity appears more real than the real one. Pastiche lays bare the way the traditional stories and themes such as love and tragedy are repackaged as frozen empty content being enjoyed over the internet as many people leave the morals of originality to methods of performing stunts.

Intertextuality unfolds the reuse of ideas of culture and historical events that did not reflect or preserve the initial meaning and were transformed into means

of self-advertising, ironic effect, or exhibition. Fragmentation reveals how the film shows how identity and stories are broken and scattered in a world full of media.

The research demonstrates the ways in which screen life films, especially in India, can represent deep theoretical concepts while interacting with local and worldwide digital culture. Through a postmodern analysis of Logout, the study provides a paradigm for comprehending how digital media shapes and destabilizes identity, narrative, and meaning. This study can aid future studies by providing a helpful lens through which to view how contemporary films represent shifts in identity, narrative, and digital culture.

Recommendations

Even though this study used a postmodern perspective to analyze Logout, there are still several topics that might be investigated further. Researchers in the future could broaden their reach through comparative research, incorporating various cultural contexts or national films, that can reveal how digital life is interpreted, comprehended, or critiqued globally. Researchers could also look at how digital storytelling

has evolved beyond cinema, for example, in web series, vlogs, or interactive media, to investigate how identity, performance, and reality are negotiated across platforms. Furthermore, this study excluded audience perspectives, focusing mainly on textual and visual analysis. Future studies could use empirical techniques like focus groups, interviews, or surveys to learn more about how audiences react to and understand the movie's depiction of digital life. This might shed more light on the narratives' emotional and cultural effects. These recommendations can help us develop a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of how digital media in the postmodern era changes identity formation, cultural expression, and story structures.

References

- Abbas, H. (2025). Exploring the Stylistic Features of Reporting Clauses in *The Alchemist* by Paulo Coelho. *Research Journal for Social Affairs*, 3(3), 373-379.
- Ahmad, M. B., Sardar, N., Begum, R., Khan, T., & Bibi, N. (2025). Analyzing Public Perception towards Beauty Creams in District Dir Lower: A Questionnaire-Based Thematic Study. *Social Science Review Archives*, 3(2), 1417-1424. 10.70670/sra.v3i2.758
- Ali, M., Hamid, M., Ejaz, A., Aziz, T., Gul, A., & Ibrahim, S. (2025). Exploring The Impact of Demographic Factors On Psychache, Life Satisfaction, And Hopelessness in Mood Disorder Patients. *Social Science Review Archives*, 3(1), 1722-1733.
- Baudrillard, J. (1983). *Simulacra and Simulation*. Trans. Sheila Glaser. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Baudrillard, J. (1994). *Simulacra and Simulation* (S. F. Glaser, Trans.). University of Michigan Press. (Original work published 1981)
- Baudrillard, J. (1994). *Simulacra and Simulation*. University of Michigan Press.
- Dhingra, R., & Mishra, M. (2025). Role of Social Media in Shaping Up Self Esteem of Adolescents. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 13(2), 3119-3128. 10.25215/1302.278
- Fatima, S. (2024). The Influence of Social Media on Adolescent Body Image Perception, Self- Esteem. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 12(2), 1317-1324.
- Hutcheon, L. (1988). *A Poetics of Postmodernism: History, Theory, Fiction*. Routledge.
- Hutcheon, L. (1989). *The Politics of Postmodernism*. Routledge. (For the distinction between parody and pastiche.)
- Ibrar, M., Ahmad, D., Humayun, T., Hashim, A., & Hussain, A. (2025). A Critical Analysis of Islamophobia in Gottschalk and Greenberg's Islamophobia: Making Muslims the Enemy. *The Critical Review of Social Sciences Studies*, 3(1), 1848-1863.
- Ijaz, F., & Rabi, F. (2022). An Exploration of Discourse Styles In Pakistani English Fictions. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(04), 357-365.
- India Today. (2025, April 17). *Logout review: Babil Khan gets likes, followers, subscribers in this tech thriller*.
- Jameson, F. (1991). *Postmodernism, or, The Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism*. Duke University Press.
- Javed Ashiq, U., Usman, T., Rabi, F., & Uzma. (2024). Dominance and hegemony: A study of Marxist class conflict in Mohsin Hamid's *Moth Smoke*. *International Journal of Contemporary Issues in Social Sciences*, 3(3), 1004-1010.
- Kristeva, J. (1980). *Desire in Language: A Semiotic Approach to Literature and Art* (T. Gora, A. Jardine, & L. S. Roudiez, Trans.). Columbia University Press.
- Lyotard, J.-F. (1979). *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge* (G. Bennington & B. Massumi, Trans.). University of Minnesota Press.
- Nawaz, A., Khan, I. U., & Rabi, F. (2024). Living in-between: Diaspora's identity crisis and hybridity in Kamila Shamsie's *Home Fire*. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 9(3), 48.
- Pande, S. (2025, April 17). *Logout movie review: Babil Khan holds the pulse in a tense, evocative thriller*. Cinema Express.

- Pathak, S., & Pandey, M. (2025). Exploring the Effects of Social Media on Self- Esteem and Mental Health among Young Adults. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 13(2), 277-281. 10.25215/1302.026
- Rabi, F., Ahmad, D., Hussain, A., & Ullah, W. (2025). The Conflict between Personal Integrity and Societal Expectations: A Psychoanalytic Analysis of Mere Pass Tum Ho. *The Critical Review of Social Sciences Studies*, 3(1), 1816-1830.
- Rabi, F., Bibi, M., Mukhtiar, M., & Zahir, K. (2025). CONSTRUCTED TO PLEASE: MEDIA AND THE SOCIAL CONSTRUCTION OF BEAUTY STANDARDS IN INDIAN MATRIMONIAL CULTURE. *Journal of Media Horizons*, 6(3), 1375-1386.
- Rabi, F., Ullah, I., & Rabi, U. (2024). Expansion of The City: An Eco-Critical Analysis of Majid Amjad's Poem "Tosee Sheher". *Educational Research and Innovation*, 4(03), 39-53.
- Rabi, F., Ullah, I., Ibrar, M., & Akbar, S. (2024). Stylistic And Structural Analysis of a ShortStory—The Good Country People Written by Flannery O'Connor. *RemittancesReview*, 9, 235-256.
- Rabi, F., Zahir, K., Aziz, L., Mukhtiar, M., & Bibi, M. (2025). Queering Motherhood: Transgender Identity and Alternative Kinship in the Vicks Ad Featuring Shreegauri Sawant: <https://doi.org/10.55966/assaj>. 2025.4. 1.0120. *ASSAJ*, 4(01), 2304-2321.
- Rehman, A. (2025). Social Media and Youth Identity Formation. *Journal of Language, Literature & Social Affairs*, 1(1), 10-19. <https://scholarclub.org/index.php/jllsa/article/view/>
- Riaz, Q., Qureshi, H., & Zaib, K. (2025). Exploring the intersection of desire, power, and aesthetic experience in Fool Me Twice. *Journal for Social Science Archives*, 3(2), 531-543.
- Samoon, S., & Juneja, A. (2025). The Impact of Social Media Usage on Self Worth and Identity among Young Adults. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Approaches in Psychology*.
- Satti, S. M. J., Zaib, K., & Mangrio, A. D. (2025). Environmental Memory and Ecological Trauma: An Ecocritical Study OfThe Memory Keeper'By Masha Gessen. *Siazga Research Journal*, 4(2), 84-93.
- Shen, Z., Zhao, M., & Zaib, K. (2025). Cultural aesthetics in language use: Examining expressive elements in novel, short story, and movie communication. *Cultura: International Journal of Philosophy of Culture and Axiology*, 20(10), 1-21.
- Shimokhin, B. (2021). Screenlife vs. Classic Cinema. *Vestnik VGIK: Journal of Film Arts and Film Studies*, 13(1), 37-44.
- The Indian Express. (2025, April 17). *Logout movie review: Babil Khan's solo act asks relevant questions but is lost in improbability*.
- Ullah, I., Ahmad, M. B., & Sardar, N. (2024). Exploring political rhetoric: Analysing contradictions, ambiguities, and anomalies in political speech by american president joe biden. *Educational Research And Innovation*, 4(02), 110-125. 10.61866/eri.v4i2.136
- Ullah, I., Bibi, M., Begam, R., Khan, T., & Bibi, N. (2024). A critical discourse analysis of language patterns and power dynamics in social media discourse. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and TESOL (JALT)*, 7(4), 914-925.
- Ullah, N., Khan, H., Qazi, A. M., Zeb, S., & Rabi, U. (2025). Emojis As A Semiotic System: Exploring Their Influence On Linguistic Simplification And Emotional Clarity In Digital Interactions. *Journal of Media Horizons*, 6(3), 2358-2379.
- Ullah, N., Khan, H., Qazi, A. M., Zeb, S., & Rabi, U. (2025). EMOJIS AS A SEMIOTIC SYSTEM: EXPLORING THEIR INFLUENCE ON LINGUISTIC SIMPLIFICATION AND EMOTIONAL CLARITY IN DIGITAL INTERACTIONS. *Journal of Media Horizons*, 6(3), 2358-2379.
- Ullah, W., Rabi, F., Khan, R., & Ahmad, H. (2025). Redefining identity: A critical analysis of transgender representation in Khuda Mera Bhi Hai. *Journal for Social Science Archives*, 3(1), 833-844.